

- E-6 Perennial; main axis of panicle slightly woolly pubescent at the base of primary branches, the rest smooth and glabrous; axis increasingly hispid-scabrid toward the tip; awns less than 5 cm long; sterile lemmas linear or linear lanceolate; rhizomatous; Australian origin; diploid *australiensis*
- E-7 Ligule with a fringe of hairs at the apex
 F-1 Perennial; plant not rhizomatous; leaves broad
 G-1 Width of leaves less than 5 cm; spikelets less than 7 mm long; American origin; tetraploid *latifolia*
 G-2 Width of leaves more than 5 cm; spikelets more than 7 mm long; American origin; tetraploid *alta*
- E-8 Ligule without fringe of hairs at the apex, leaves less than 2 cm broad
 F-2 Width of spikelets less than 2 mm
 G-3 Panicle branches not spreading; length of spikelets 4.5-6.0 mm, width 15 - 2.0 mm; culm base slender, hard and not spongy; ligule less than 3.5 mm, never split, hard, flexuous with fine bristles; sterile lemmas acuminate and narrowly triangular; African origin; perennial; diploid *eichingeri*
 G-4 Length of spikelets 3.7 - 4.7 mm; width usually less than 2 mm; panicle small with spreading branches; awned (2 cm or less) or awnless; Asian origin; perennial; tetraploid *minuta*
- F-3 Width of spikelet more than 2 mm
 G-5 Length of spikelets more than 5 mm; width 2.0-2.5 mm; culm base soft and spongy, ligule longer than 3.0 mm, soft, and split when dried; straight or flexuous with rigid bristles; panicle loose with spreading branches; sterile lemmas acute and triangular; African origin; perennial; tetraploid *punctata*
- E-9 Ligule glabrous or hairy; length of spikelets less than 5 mm, width almost always more than 2 mm; awns often shorter than 2 cm, or awnless; occasionally rhizomatous; Asian origin; perennial; diploid *crus*
- A-2 Sterile lemmas subulate or setaceous
 B-2 Surface of sterile lemmas and palea granulate; sterile lemmas minute, long, tapered from base; usually awnless
 C-3 Spikelets oblong to elliptic oblong, shorter than 7 mm; Asian origin; perennial; diploid *granulata*
 C-4 Spikelets narrowly oblong to lanceolate, longer than 7 mm; Asian origin; perennial; diploid *meyeriana*
- B-3 Surface of lemma and palea not granulate; awned; spikelets 8-17 mm long
 C-5 Lemma ciliate along keel, without wing; leaves herbaceous
 D-6 Awns 6-15 mm long; sterile lemmas shorter than lemma; Asian origin; perennial; tetraploid *ridleyi*
 D-7 Awns 16-36 mm long; sterile lemmas as long as or longer than lemma; New Guinean origin; perennial; tetraploid *longiglumis*
- B-4 Surface of lemma almost smooth with fine longitudinally dotted stippled surface
 C-6 Spikelets linear, 1-2 mm wide; awns 6-17 mm long; sterile lemmas always much shorter than lemma; African origin; annual; diploid *brachyantha*
- A-3 Spikelets 15 - 1.75 mm long; nodes hairy; New Guinean origin *schlechteri*

NOTES

1. Excluded from the key are taxa of doubtful validity or names of uncertain application: *O. abromeitiana*, *O. collina*, *O. fatua*, *O. malampuzhaensis*, *O. perennis*, *O. perennis* subsp. *cubensis*, *O. schweinfurthiana*, *O. stapfii*, *O. ubanghensis*, and *O. indandamanica*.
2. Removed from the genus *Oryza* are taxa formerly known as '*O. angustifolia*', '*O. perrieri*', and '*O. tisseranti*' - to the genus *Leersia*; '*O. coarctata*' (renamed as *Porteresia coarctata*); and '*O. subulata*' (to the genus *Rhynchoriza*).
3. For specimens of uncertain morphological identity, a determination of somatic chromosome numbers from young root-tips will be helpful in certain cases.
4. Annual and perennial growth habits are rather difficult to distinguish when the plants are grown under tropical conditions; the term "annual" refers to a primary seed-propagated form while "perennial" refers to a taxon adapted to vegetative propagation by underground plant parts.

^aFormerly known as *O. breviligulata*, includes the weed race *O. stapfii*.

Efficiency of wide compatibility gene

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In breeding for tolerance for low temperature and problem soils, we use varieties having the wide compatibility gene to combine agronomic traits of japonica and indica varieties.

In the 1987 wet season, we used 3 varieties with the wide compatibility gene (BPI-176 [indica], N22 [aus], and Moroberekan [japonica]) to make 66 single crosses involving a range of indicas and japonicas, and one tongil (indica/japonica hybrid). Hybrid seeds were planted in the IIRRI F₁ nursery in 1988 dry season.

Spikelet fertility of hybrids between ordinary varieties (female parent) and those with the wide compatibility gene (male parent). IIRRI, 1988 dry season.

Female parent	Spikelet fertility (%)		
	BPI-76	N22	Moroberekan
<i>Indica</i>			
ARC6000	83.0	96.9	91.0
China 1039	90.7	86.2	87.4
IR4630-22-2-5-1-3	91.9	66.6	70.1
IR9884-54-3-1E-P1	84.4	72.3	86.0
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	79.4	36.6	75.3
IR32843-92-2-2-3	95.0	79.4	71.6
IR44670-168-2-3-1	96.5	84.2	72.4
Nona Bokra	95.5	31.8	84.4
SR26B	92.3	76.9	72.3
<i>Japonica</i>			
Akihikari	43.3	81.0	97.0
Barkat	30.3	59.3	90.9
Sasanishiki	23.6	69.8	95.5
Ta-mao-tao	33.1	59.6	89.6
Tatsumi mochi	78.8	53.2	86.7
<i>Tongil</i>			
Milyang 54	92.1	40.8	93.0
Mean	74.0	66.3	84.2
SD	26.7	19.3	9.4

At maturity, 10 main panicles were randomly harvested to determine spikelet fertility for each cross (see table). BPI-76 showed normal fertility with indicas, the tongil, and one japonica. Fertility with N22 was highly variable among japonicas or indicas.

Fertility was normal in all crosses with Moroberekan.

Thus, the efficacy of the wide compatibility gene varies from variety to variety. Although the gene of Moroberekan was very effective, it may not be the best to use in breeding

programs because of its poor performance under lowland conditions. Acceptable varieties with efficient wide adaptability gene need to be isolated or developed. □

Breeding methods

Sensitivity of upland rice genotypes to gamma radiation

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We irradiated 3 genotypes of upland rice—Sathi 34-36, a local high-yielding, late, and tall genotype; IET2473, dwarf, mid-early, and coarse-grained; and Culture 102-5, semidwarf with medium duration and long, fine grain—with 5, 10, 15, and 20 kR doses of gamma rays. The experiment, with 2 replications, measured germination percentage, and root and shoot length at 10 d after planting.

Germination percentage was not appreciably reduced by gamma radiation. Root lengths were progressively reduced from 0 kR (7.14 cm) to 20 kR (3.82 cm) (see figure). Of the 3 genotypes, Culture 102-5 had longest roots at 0 kR and shortest at 20 kR. Gamma radiation did not reduce shoot lengths except in Culture 102-5.

Analysis of variance confirmed that radiation effects on root and shoot lengths varied significantly among varieties. The root length of Culture 102-5 was reduced 0.30 cm for every kR unit increase in radiation, compared to an average of 0.09 cm/kR unit for the 2 other varieties. Radiation reduced shoot

Effect of gamma ray doses on root and shoot lengths of 3 upland rice genotypes. Gujarat, India, 1987.

length of Culture 102-5, increased those of Sathi 34-36, but had no effect on those of IET2473.

We used rate of reduction in all three seedling characters per unit increase of

kR as the criteria for measuring sensitivity.

Culture 102-5 was clearly the most sensitive among the varieties tested. □